

BLENDED LEARNING AS A MEAN TO ENHANCE EDUCATIONAL QUALITY

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Abstract

The integration of technology into education through models like blended learning is rapidly altering traditional teaching methods. Blended learning combines online instruction with face-to-face classroom experiences. As policies are developed to support this new approach, it's crucial to understand the theoretical underpinnings of blended learning, explore effective implementation strategies, and recognize its growing importance in a dynamic educational landscape. This research paper reviews existing studies to examine the theoretical basis and adoption of blended learning as a means of enhancing education quality. Furthermore, it analyses the factors that influence both the adoption and implementation of this model. The study concludes that blended learning encompasses a range of elements for students, including face-to-face interactions, activities, resources, assessments, and feedback. For educators, it involves technology integration, pedagogical approaches, content development, and knowledge acquisition. Ultimately, the findings aim to provide valuable insights into the adoption and implementation of blended learning for students, teachers, and administrators alike.

Key Words: *Blended Learning, Face-to-Face learning, Quality Education.*

1. Introduction

The use of blended learning in education is rapidly increasing because it combines the advantages of both traditional and online learning approaches. Previous studies find that the blended learning approach enhances students' learning engagement and experience because it has a significant impact on students' awareness of the teaching mode and learning background. Blended learning emphasizes learning from teaching, thus enabling students to become more involved and more excited about the learning process and, as a result, improving their persistence and commitment. Poon (2014) concluded that blended learning is likely to develop

as a leading learning approach for the future as one of the top ten educational trends in the twenty-first century. He further says that the question is not whether blended learning should be adopted in education, but rather the question should be related to the practices that should be included for successful blended learning implementation.

The phrase blended learning was first associated with classroom training to e-learning activities. Accordingly, blended learning is the integration of traditional face-to-face and e-learning teaching paradigm. Blended learning employs a combination of online-mediated and face-to-face instruction to enable teachers to develop algorithmic and creative reasoning skills in students, enhance teaching qualities, and achieve social distancing can help in achieving the goal (Subramaniam and Muniyandi, 2019). Blended learning involves a combination of different methods of teaching, learning styles, and types of teaching (Kaur, 2013). It is often used with terms such as integrated, flexible, mixed mode, multi-mode or hybrid learning.

Blended learning involves the integration of different initiatives, which is achieved by combining 30% face-to-face interaction with 70% IT mediated learning (Anthony et al. 2019). Similarly, Owston et al. (2019) recommended that a successful blended learning delivery consists of 80% high quality online learning integrated with 20% classroom teaching that engages with online content. Respectively, blended learning is a combination of different didactic approaches (cooperative learning, discovery learning expository, presentations etc.) and delivery methods (personal communication, broadcasting, publishing, etc.) (Graham 2013). Various research has found that online systems have the potential to provide a platform for strategies capable of offering an alternative to the real-life environment, providing a useful learning opportunity for students that improves the quality of learning. Helps in improving. When designed judiciously and accurately, IT can be deployed to achieve an authentic learning experience with practical relevance to engage and motivate students. Thus, blended learning allows students to not only clarify the learning but also test the knowledge gained through the semester.

Furthermore, blended learning provides flexibility for students and teachers, improves personalization, improves student outcomes, encourages the development of autonomy and self-directed learning, creates possibilities for professional learning, and reduces costs. Reduces efficiency, increases communication between students and teachers, and between students. Blended learning encourages the reform of educational policies with the possibility of reclaiming the ideals of educational institutions (Heinz and Proctor 2004). Blended learning seeks to create a harmonious and consistent balance between online access to knowledge and

traditional human teaching by considering the perspectives of students and teachers. Therefore, blended learning remains an important educational concept as its main focus is on providing the most effective teaching and learning experience (Wang et al. 2004).

Blended learning provides access to online resources and information that meet students' level of knowledge and interest. It supports teaching situations by providing opportunities for professional collaboration, and also improves teachers' time efficiency. Blended learning enhances student engagement in their own learning, allows students to study at their own pace, and prepares students for the future by providing real-world skills that help students achieve their academic goals. Skills, self-learning abilities and of course computer knowledge helps to apply in the workforce.

Blended learning improves social communication in communities of educational institutions, improves students' competence and self-reliance, increases the quality of learning, improves critical thinking in educational environments and helps students communicate course content. (Bailey et al. 2015). Existing studies mainly consider blended learning in the context of students and teachers to improve teaching and learning. Previous studies have focused on adopting blended learning to improve student learning and the quality of teachers' teaching. But only a few studies explored the blended learning implementation process. To fill this gap in knowledge, this current study aimed to systematically review and synthesize prior studies exploring blended learning adoption and implementation related to students, teachers, and administration based on the following two research questions:

1. What is the structure of the theory and principles employed in blended learning study?
2. What are the factors that influence students, teachers, and administrators to adopt and implement blended learning?

2. Literature review

Learning in education refers to the process of acquiring new knowledge, skills, intellectual abilities that can be used to successfully solve problems. The use of technologies in teaching and learning is not a new paradigm in education (Poon 2012). Undoubtedly, students in the twenty-first century are familiar with the digital environment and hence teachers are encouraged to use information technology (IT) in teaching to stimulate and plan student learning. Teaching and learning with the help of blended learning strategies has become a common teaching approach to engage students in learning (Garrison and Kanuka 2004). Thus, blended learning has progressed to include diverse teaching strategies and is renowned as one of the leading trends in education. Blended learning provides increased academic productivity,

knowledge access, group collaboration, personal development, cost efficiency, simplifies reforms, and solves attendance-related problems (Mustapa et al. 2015). Previous studies have concluded that blended learning is both productive and beneficial compared to traditional e-learning.

Blended learning in education is a popular approach to creating a more collaborative and welcoming learning environment to reduce student anxiety and fear of making mistakes. Blended learning was adopted in educational institutions in the late 1990s, it gained widespread acceptance in the 2000s with many more educational institutions offering courses in blended mode (Graham et al. 2013). Blended learning combines online-mediated and face-to-face instruction to help teachers achieve educational goals in developing algorithmic and creative reasoning skills, enhancing teaching qualities, and training students to help achieve social order. Employs combination (Kaur, 2013). Some researchers argued that technology integration in teaching promotes learning through discovery and adds interactivity and more motivation, leading to better feedback, social interaction, and use of course materials.

Figure 1: Blended Learning

As shown in **Figure 1**, blended learning implementations typically include face-to-face and other related online learning delivery methods. Typically, students attend traditional teacher-directed face-to-face classes with computer-mediated tools to create a blended learning

environment to gain experience and promote student learning success and engagement. In fact, Graham et al. (2013) predicted that blended learning would become the new curriculum delivery model that would employ various media resources to strengthen interactions among students. Blended learning provides motivating and meaningful learning through various asynchronous and synchronous learning strategies, such as social networking, live chat, webinars, blogs, etc. that provide more opportunities for reflection and feedback from students (Graham, 2013).

There has been rapid growth in the adoption of blended learning with a focus on improving teaching and learning outcomes, thus prior studies have assessed the effectiveness of blended learning by comparing traditional teaching and online learning. However, there are limited studies that examined the theoretical foundations of blended learning adoption and implementation for teaching and learning, and very limited studies focused on examining administrative adoption related to blended learning. To this end, Garrison and Kanuka (2004) noted that it is important to examine blended learning adoption from the perspective of institutions' administrators. However, research focusing on blended learning adoption and implementation is limited, and this is a gap that should be addressed. Given the above insights, it is felt that there is a need for more blended learning-based research to guide policy makers to strategically adopt blended learning in education towards improving learning and teaching. Therefore, this study systematically reviews and synthesizes prior studies that explored the adoption and implementation of blended learning by students, teachers, and administrators.

3. Methodology

It is important to conduct a comprehensive literature review before beginning any research investigation. The literature review explores existing research gaps and reveals areas where prior studies have not fully explored. Similarly, a systematic literature review is a review that is based on clear research questions, defines and explores relevant studies, and finally assesses the quality of the studies based on specified criteria.

4. Structures and factors related to adopting blended learning in education

Figure 2: Constructs and factors related to adopting blended learning in education

Adoption of blended learning cannot be achieved by simply integrating online and face-to-face teaching modes. Thus, there is a need to identify the structures that influence students, teachers, and administrators to adopt blended learning strategies that play a vital role in ensuring successful blended learning experiences in education. On this, educationists like Machado (2007) highlighted that successful implementation of blended learning initiatives requires an alignment between administrative, teachers, students' educational goals. It is important to examine the structures related to human computer interaction to assess which structures contribute to realizing the desired teaching and learning objectives involving teachers and students. Therefore, this study investigates the blended learning strategies implemented by students and teachers in education.

5. Conclusion and Implications

Firstly, the review shows that the ad hoc approach is the most commonly employed approach by prior studies in developing research models to investigate blended learning adoption in education, followed by TAM, and then IS Success Model, then UTAUT and finally DoI is the principle. Practically, the findings of this study may be useful in supporting teachers in teaching and preparing best practices to implement inventive approaches that promote blended learning

to enhance teaching and learning outcomes that can be used in higher Blended learning is used in education to refer to a system of methods for adoption. The findings of this study indicate that blended learning practices derived from the literature including face-to-face, activities, information, resources, assessment, and feedback are deployed by teachers to design appropriate instructional strategies to help students Can help in improving learning. These findings provide guidelines on the design and implementation of blended learning practices. This study shows that teachers' decisions to successfully implement blended learning practices are determined by the ease of managing online course services. Thus, consideration of availability of computer hardware and software resources, academic support, financial aid and promotion should be provided by the institute management. For administrators, this study provides a policy roadmap for the adoption of blended learning in education.

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